

DISCIPLINE AND THE DYAD OF "MASTER-STUDY"

Satorov Sardor Abdimuradovich

Teacher at Termiz State Pedagogical Institute

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Abstract. *The article describes the recommendations for taking into account the human factor in the processes of modeling the conflicts of the "teacher-student" dyad. The studied "teacher-student" dyad, the whole educational process is considered as a humanistic system, which ensures a significant increase in the development of the student's personality through the use of systematic analysis and decision-making methods.*

Keywords: *students are undisciplined, teacher-student dyad, conflict, modeling, human factor, humanitarian system, systematic analysis and decision-making methods.*

Indiscipline is the manifestation of students' behavior that deviates from the generally accepted norms in a particular educational society, which prevents the teacher from fulfilling his professional duties and the education of other students. This helps to create a conflict, which can be resolved by applying certain educational corrective measures to the student. On the other hand, the conflict can be provoked by a certain charisma of the teacher. Therefore, the issue of complex modeling of conflicts, taking into account the individual characteristics of teachers and students and the specific characteristics of antidotes used to correct the appropriate discipline, is relevant.

In our opinion, it is now generally recognized that the quality of the educational process in educational institutions, first of all, the organization of the activities of the "teacher-student" group can be optimized based on systematic analysis methods. Some of them are clearly described in pedagogical works [2; 6; 8], but they did not pay attention to modeling the working processes of the "master-student" dyad and their improvement.

It is worth noting that local researchers do not pay enough attention to the issue of students' lack of discipline, taking into account the motivation of students to study, which creates "wrong links" in the continuous chain of improvement of the educational process that is constantly implemented in schools. On the other hand, although indirectly, the study of the formulated problem still continues in research on the formation of professional culture and professional responsibility of students [9; 10].

In some research works, the results of direct quality measurement and discipline diagnostics are summarized [2]. However, taking into account the personal charisma of the first and the indiscipline of the second, the problems of modeling the interaction of the participants of the "master-student" dyad have been studied in a limited number of works [3; 12].

We emphasize that the teacher uses one or another antidote based on personal charisma, educational and educational work experience, as well as the disciplinary practice adopted in a particular school. If the interaction of the elements of the "teacher-student" binary (dyad) is considered a conflict, then in the practice of scientific research, mathematical game theory methods are usually used to model conflict situations in any field of human activity [4].

According to the definition of L. Zade, "man himself (individual) and his thought processes can be considered as humanistic systems. Depending on the goals that a person fulfills in the humanistic system, some classes of humanistic systems can be distinguished" [6]. In particular, the humanitarian education system is the goal of the activities of a specialist pedagogical or pedagogical

team to provide students with the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities, including the ability to learn.

The given definitions determine the need to take into account the human factor in modeling the working processes of the "teacher-student" dyad. On the other hand, the activity of the participant of the educational process (teacher, student) can be imagined as a series of continuous decisions made and implemented under the influence of many factors of different nature (internal / external, objective / subjective) [2; 18]. Therefore, the appropriate methods, technologies, and procedures must be truly based on a system analysis and decision-making methodology.

As part of our research, we will focus on game theory methods. Each practical conflict situation in the educational process is complex, and its analysis is complicated by the presence of certain factors. To analyze the conflict mathematically, a mathematical model called a game is built. Game theory is a mathematical theory of conflict situations. Its purpose is to develop recommendations on the reasonable behavior of the parties to the conflict. It serves as a basis for the study of human behavior when making choices in conditions of risk or uncertain information, when the probability of the environmental state is unknown or partially determined by an opponent - another participant in the conflict. That's why we call the participants of the educational process, the players and their interaction, which make up the dyad "teacher-student" - a game. The development of the game in time can be presented as a series of actions of the participants.

Based on certain normative recommendations or personal experience of educational work, the teacher independently and consciously chooses a reaction strategy to the student's unruly behavior. In a real conflict, the optimal strategy is often to anticipate and exploit what is a flaw in the opponent's knowledge or strategy. For example, when an unruly student learns about a teacher's behavior, he or she creates an image of what characteristic of his or her unruly behavior causes the teacher to react violently and immediately. Let's say that the systematic lateness to the lesson bothers a certain teacher more, because he has to react by forbidding or allowing the student to enter the classes with an explanation about his lateness, and at the same time disrupting his personal work rhythm. When such delays occur in succession due to the discipline of several students, the teacher's reaction becomes increasingly severe. At the same time, if a student is impulsive, trying to get the result as quickly as possible, without thinking about its correctness, the same teacher can treat him more leniently. Because reacting to a hasty and incorrect decision of an educational task, on the one hand, it reveals to everyone present the methodological mistakes made by an impulsive student in the process of solving it, at the same time shows the wrongness of such behavior, and on the other hand, it shows the position of those who solved it. increases. The game differs from the real conflict because it is conducted according to certain rules that indicate the rights and obligations of the participants.

We assume that the teacher's strategy, that is, the set of rules that determines the choice of the influence option for each individual action depending on the developed educational situation, is characterized by his style (whether the teacher tends to exaggerate or underestimate the grades, or whether he presents them objectively).

Particular attention should be paid to the concrete activity of the obtained results, which gives students a better understanding of the educational situation, to evaluate each decision from different (sometimes contradictory) points of view, to consider its advantages and disadvantages, and in the end the decision, if not the only correct one, then in the extreme case, it is contrived and drawn to the end. It is about thinking and considering decisions in the learning process, where

the consequences of discipline should be the application of certain educational measures, including punishment, to the student. First of all, this is called allocentrism, which means an approach to analyzing a conflict situation from the point of view of the opposing party. For example, the student develops the ability to predict the teacher's reaction to the manifestation of discipline: what the teacher will do and what the consequences will be for the violator.

There is a clear and definite conclusion that there is no point in spending money and time on the education of students of below average ability. This indirectly also confirms once again the need for stricter selection of students in schools, which leads to the following firm conclusion about the need to increase the requirements for the results obtained by students according to the data of external expertise.

The following should be noted as the most important individual scientific results. For the first time, studies were carried out on the adaptation of game theory methods to model the conflict between "teacher-student". Its results show that students understand the diversity of the final results of their educational activities, the teacher's personal attitude to self-learning, abilities and behavior.

According to the readers, the following was determined:

- if the student is talented and diligent, attends the class, he will receive at least 8 points from the teacher whose leadership style is bureaucratic and tends to underestimate grades;
- if the student has a high reading ability, is diligent and attends classes, he will receive a grade of 7.1 points from the most demanding teacher;
- a student with an average level of ability, if he attends classes and studies diligently, gets a grade in the range of 5.2-7.8 points;
- if a student with below average ability, but tries, attends classes, he can get a maximum score from a teacher with an anarchic leadership style who tends to overestimate grades - 5.1 points.

However, the presented research results can be used to improve educational work in universities. Also, it should be noted that it is necessary to assign certain appropriateness coefficients to the standards and to clarify them through more detailed quantitative modeling of the studied conflict.

In conclusion, indiscipline is a violation of the student's attitude to study, conflicting relationships, psychogenic diseases and reactions, increased levels of anxiety, formation of incorrect mechanisms in the development of the student's personality.

At the root of these problems are complex personal and social attitudinal factors. These factors have a serious negative impact on the formation of a student as a well-rounded person. In most cases, such situations happen to students as a result of incorrect pedagogical requirements being imposed on them.

REFERENCES

1. Камишин В. В. Методи системного аналізу у кваліметрії навчально–виховного процесу [Текст]: Монографія / В. В. Камишин, О. М. Рєва. – К.: ІУД НАПН України, 2012. – 270 с.
2. Эффективность технических систем [Текст] / Под общ. ред. В. Ф. Уткина, Ю. В. Крючкова // Надежность и эффективность в технике: Справочник в 10 т. – М.: Машиностроение, 1988. – Т. 3. – 328 с.

3. Замков О. О. Математические методы в экономике [Текст]: Учеб. / О. О. Замков, А. В. Толстопятенко, Ю. Н. Черемных; Общ. ред. д.э.н. проф. А. В. Сидоровича. – М.: Дело и Сервис, 2001. – 368 с.
4. Таха Х. А. Введение в исследование операций [Текст]: Пер. с англ. / Х. А. Таха. – 6–е издание – М.: Вильямс, 2001. – 912 с.
5. Заде Л. Понятие лингвистической переменной и его применение к принятию приближенных решений [Текст] / Л. Заде; Под ред. Н. Н. Моисеева, С. А. Орловского; Пер. с англ. Н. И. Ринго. – М.: Мир, 1976. – 165 с.